

Thin Layer Chromatography of Metal Ions Complexed with Anils—Part III

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Separation and quantitative estimation of complexes of bidentate and monodentate ligands *p*-Dimethylaminoanil of 4-hydroxy 1-Naphthyl glyoxal and *p*-Dimethylaminoanil of 4-Acetyl 1-naphthol respectively with some 3d transition metal ions viz. Cr(III), Mn(II), Fe(III), Co(II), Cu(II) have been made by Thin Layer Chromatographic technique using silica gel as an adsorbent with starch as binder.

TAKING advantage of the rapid and better separability of organic compounds by the TLC method complexes have been chosen instead of metal ions as the migrating species. In continuation of our work^{1,2} present communication describing TLC investigation in metal anil complexes, provided a very simple and convenient method for the identification and separation of metal ion mixtures and explored the possibility of detection and subsequent rapid separation and estimation of the elements in different ores and minerals.

Long persisting dark colours of the complexes explored spectrophotometric determination of metal ions and rendered the spots self discernible and no developer is required to identify the metal species ; thus chromatogram is undisturbed from the effects of spraying.

Our early investigations³⁻⁵ in the coordination properties of *p*-dimethylaminoanil of 4-hydroxyl 1-naphthyl glyoxal (A) and *p*-dimethylaminoanil of 4-acetyl 1-naphthol (B) used, have suggested that A acts as bidentate ligand with coordination centres at carbonyl oxygen and azomethine nitrogen and B acts as monodentate ligand with donor ability at azomethine nitrogen during interaction with metal ions. Hydroxyl group being at remoter position to the donor groups does not participate in complexation. Typical complex formation is shown below :

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Experimental

Preparation and Development of plates

Silica gel (N.C.L. Poona, India) having been freed from iron and chloride ions and mixed with starch (E. Merck, Garmatadt, G.F.R.) as binder (19 : 1, w/w), was used for coating the glass plates. An aqueous slurry was used to prepare the layers of 0.10 cm. thickness with a homebuilt apparatus⁶. The coated plates were dried at 100° for 2 hr in an oven. Complex solutions prepared in dioxane and metal solutions prepared in water from their analytical grade metal chlorides, were applied with fine capillaries. The R_F values were determined on 20×50 cm and 20×15 cm glass plates. The plates were developed in glass chambers with ground-in lids by the ascending technique.

Synthesis of Ligands and Complexes

The isolation and characterisation of both the ligands and their complexes under study have already been reported^{3,4}.

Optical density measurements :

All the spectrophotometric measurements have been made on 'Spectronic-20' spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

The R_F values of the complexes chromatographed individually using different solvents with silica gel

TABLE 1 SPOT-COLOUR, λ_{max} , R_F VALUES OF COMPLEXED 3-d METAL IONS

Complex	Spot-Colour	λ_{max} (m μ)	MeCH	Dioxane	Me ₂ CO	MeOH	EtOH	BuOH	(BuOH:AcOH) AcOH	(4:1,v/v)	(3:2,v/v)	(2:3,v/v)	(1:4,v/v)	(1:4,v/v)
A	Dark brown	460	0.46	0.12	0.11	0.76	0.76	0.87	0.68	0.73	0.85	0.81	0.73	0.20
(CrA ₃ Cl ₃)Cl	Light Gray	445	0.29	0.35	0.17	0.82	0.90	0.86	0.87	0.82	0.73	0.83	0.85	0.39
(MnA ₃ Cl ₃)	Dirty Yellow	430	0.45	0.26	0.12	0.84	0.82	0.89	0.91	0.83	0.72	0.82	0.86	0.15
(FeA ₃ Cl ₃)Cl	Dirty Brown	440	0.22	0.16	0.10	0.80	0.82	0.87	0.91	0.84	0.26	0.83	0.79	0.15
(CoACl ₃)	Gray	430	0.30	0.38	0.10	0.81	0.84	0.37	0.88	0.84	0.72	0.83	0.85	0.16
(CuACl ₃)	Gray	440	0.05	0.14	0.18	0.77	0.87	0.22	0.90	0.71	0.71	0.81	0.83	0.12
B	Pink	580	0.43	0.05	0.06	0.70	0.71	0.83	0.62	0.75	0.79	0.83	0.85	0.15
(CrB ₃ Cl ₃ ·2H ₂ O)Cl	Dirty Brown	600	0.03	0.10	0.09	0.86	0.91	0.05	0.89	0.85	0.37	0.82	0.83	0.03
(MnB ₃ Cl ₃ ·2H ₂ O)	Yellowish	560	0.08	0.10	0.17	0.78	0.80	0.89	0.89	0.80	0.35	0.81	0.86	0.14
(FeB ₃ Cl ₃ ·2H ₂ O)Cl	Light Yellow	520	0.03	0.10	—	0.76	0.76	—	0.91	0.85	—	0.81	0.86	—
(CoBCl ₃ ·H ₂ O)	Light Brown	660	0.03	0.09	0.05	0.81	0.80	—	0.90	0.84	0.23	0.80	0.78	0.04
(CuBCl ₃ ·H ₂ O)	Dirty Gray	560	0.04	0.11	0.05	0.85	0.76	0.07	0.86	0.83	0.31	0.85	0.79	0.12
Development time	—	—	1h	2h	1h	1h	2h	2h	3h	4h	3h	3h	2h	1h

Room temperature 20°C

absorbent are noted in Table I. The R_F values of metal complexes after being complexed with each ligand present in solvent (0.03 g/100 ml) have been found not appreciably different (~ 0.01) from the values reported in Table I. These results explored the separation of mixture of all the five metal ions in methyl cyanide with *p*-dimethylaminoanil of 4-hydroxyl 1-naphthyl glyoxal. *p*-Dimethylaminoanil of 4-acetyl 1-naphthol has been found less effective as it could separate binary mixtures of metal ions.

In the mixture analysis of metals Cr(III), Mn(II), Fe(III), Co(II) and Cu(II) the mixture of their very dilute solutions was used and 0.03 g/100 ml of solvent of ligand A was added in the solvent. The R_F values of the adducts when their mixture was applied, were also found unchanged from the values (Table 1) for each component if migrated from the individual point of application. The rates of migrations of the complexed species were quite different which evidently showed their separation. In spite of partial overlapping of the coloured spots and trailing the intensified colours of the chromatogram components did not obscure the possibility of their separation and identification.

The R_F values of the metal complexes vary with the layer thickness but are independent of plate size. The trailing effect in acetic acid was maximum and decreased by mixing butanol in which no migrating spot is accompanied with the trail. Abnormal R_F values obtained in the mixtures than that of acetic acid or butanol may be attributed to the formation of azeotropic mixtures.

Quantitative Estimations :

Quantitative estimations of metal ions were made spectrophotometrically only with ligand A. However λ_{max} were recorded for both the ligands and their complexes and values are noted in Table-I. The absorption by ligand A at λ_{max} of each complex was quite negligible. Subsequent spectrophotometric studies were carried out at λ_{max} of each adduct.

In order to the minimum amount of reagent necessary for determination of metal the optical density at λ_{max} of a series of solutions containing reagent and metal in the molar ratios of 0.5 : 1 to 9 : 1 were determined. Curves plotted between optical density and moles of reagents added, were straight lines upto the molar ratio of 1 : 2 in the case of Cr(III), Mn(II), Fe(III) and 1 : 1 in the case of Co(II), Cu(II). These results evidently showed that an excess of reagent to the above ratio did not effect the optical density of the complex.

The chromatogram fragments were scrapped and components were eluted with dioxane. The elutes were employed for spectrophotometric determination of metals in their mixture. The optical density at λ_{max} of the metal complex so produced was measured and concentration of corresponding metal in elute was deduced from a standard calibration curve (Fig. 1) obtained under similar conditions. For preparing calibration curves 5.0 ml of $1.00 \times 10^{-3} M$ ligand was mixed with different volumes of $0.50 \times 10^{-3} M$ metal solutions and total volume was kept constant to 15 ml. The curves 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 correspond to Cr^{3+} , Mn^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Co^{2+} and Cu^{2+} respectively.

FIG. 1. CALIBRATION CURVES

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